

**THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF
ATTRACTING FUTURE SPORTS TEACHERS TO RESEARCH WORK**

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Abstract: The main task of the education system is to create the necessary conditions for the formation and development of personality on the basis of national and universal values, achievements of science and practice. In general, we can say that research work as an activity consists of several stages: planning, building a hypothesis, conducting research, writing a scientific paper. The last stage is a kind of result of the work done. The main methods for studying the physical development of a person are external examination (somatoscopy) and measurements - anthropometry (somatometry). The level of physical development and the degree of its harmony are determined using anthropometric research methods.

Key words: research activities/ patterns of phenomena/ process of conducting research/ level of physical development.

**ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ СИСТЕМЫ
ПРИВЛЕЧЕНИЯ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ СПОРТА К НАУЧНО-
ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКОЙ РАБОТЕ**

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Аннотация: Главная задача системы образования - создание необходимых условий для формирования и развития личности на основе национальных и общечеловеческих ценностей, достижений науки и практики. В целом можно сказать, что научно-исследовательская работа как деятельность состоит из нескольких этапов: планирование, построение гипотезы, проведение исследования, написание научной работы. Последний этап представляет собой своеобразный результат проведенной работы. Основными методами исследования физического развития человека являются внешний осмотр (соматоскопия) и измерения — антропометрия (соматометрия). Определяют уровень физического развития и степень его гармоничности с помощью методов антропометрических исследований.

Ключевые слова: научно-исследовательская деятельность/ закономерности явлений/ процесс проведения исследование/ уровень физического развития.

Scientific research activities are aimed at identifying objectively existing patterns of phenomena and processes occurring in the socio-natural environment and replenishing knowledge about the world.

Research work is work of a scientific nature associated with scientific search, conducting research, experiments in order to expand existing and obtain new knowledge, test scientific hypotheses, establish patterns, scientific generalizations and justifications. In general, we can say

that research work as an activity consists of several stages: planning, building a hypothesis, conducting research, writing a scientific paper. The last stage is a kind of result of the work done.

The main task of the education system is to create the necessary conditions for the formation and development of personality on the basis of national and universal values, achievements of science and practice.

Stages of planning a scientific study

1. Allocation of tasks and assessment of resources...
2. Determining the time frame...
3. Construction of chronological order...
4. Conducting a critical analysis...
5. Reporting the results of the study...
6. Monitoring the progress of the study

To formulate a hypothesis, you first need to imagine how the scientific questions addressed in your work might affect the phenomena or processes in question. Then, in the practical section, you need to conduct a thorough analysis or series of experiments to confirm or refute your hypothesis.

In recent years, there has been an increased interest of the population in their own health. However, it is noteworthy that interest in one's own health awakens in adulthood, most often already when the body can only be treated. It often happens that a person, through an incorrect lifestyle, bad habits, physical inactivity, and overeating, by the age of 20-30 brings himself to a catastrophic state and only then remembers medicine.

In the world community, the degree of success of a state is assessed by the health of its citizens. At this stage, the Russian government is taking active measures to strengthen and preserve the health of its citizens: a law banning smoking has been adopted, a Ministry of Physical Education and Sports has been organized, newspapers, magazines, television and radio programs on health issues have been published, and advertising has been published. However, the statistics remain deplorable: the number of diseases and injuries is growing inexorably. Here are just a few facts: in 1990, the number of non-communicable diseases accounted for 55% of all registered diseases, and by 2020 their number is projected to increase to 73% (if the situation and the rate of increase in incidence remain the same). The most common form of cancer is lung cancer (most common in smokers). The main cause of disability in men today is alcoholism.

Health is the most valuable thing we have. It cannot be bought for any money. Health needs to be strengthened and preserved. The formation of a healthy lifestyle depends only on ourselves, our preferences, beliefs and worldviews.

In our time, during the scientific, technological and industrial revolution, almost everything is done for a person by machines, depriving him of motor activity. The main share of physical activity comes from sports and physical education. For which we, as always, do not have the opportunity, time, strength, desire, etc. Hence poor health, lethargy, illness, obesity, and other ailments.

Hypothesis: if we identify the influence of physical culture on the formation of a healthy lifestyle, then it will be possible to give practical recommendations to increase motivation to lead a healthy lifestyle.

A special place in a healthy life regime belongs to the daily routine, a certain rhythm of human life and activity. Each person's routine should include a certain time for work, rest, eating, and sleep.

The daily routine of different people can and should be different depending on the nature of the work, living conditions, habits and inclinations, however, even here there must be a certain daily rhythm and daily routine. It is necessary to provide sufficient time for sleep and rest. Breaks between meals should not exceed 5-6 hours. When we talk about a daily routine, we do not mean strict schedules with a minute-by-minute time budget for each task for each day. However, the routine itself is a kind of core on which the conduct of both weekdays and weekends should be based.

A rational regime of work and rest is a necessary element of a healthy lifestyle. With a correct and strictly observed regime, a clear and necessary rhythm of the body's functioning is developed, which creates optimal conditions for work and rest, and thereby promotes health, improves performance and increases productivity.

Labor is the true core and basis of a person's healthy life regimen. There is a misconception about the harmful effects of labor, which allegedly causes "wear and tear" of the body, excessive consumption of energy and resources, and premature aging. Labor, both physical and mental, is not only not harmful, but on the contrary, a systematic, feasible, and well-organized labor process has an extremely beneficial effect on the nervous system, heart and blood vessels, the musculoskeletal system - on the entire human body. Constant training during labor strengthens our body. He who works hard and well throughout his life lives long. On the contrary, idleness leads to muscle weakness, metabolic disorders, obesity and premature decrepitude.

The next component of a healthy lifestyle is balanced nutrition. When talking about it, you should remember two basic laws, the violation of which is dangerous to health.

Firstly, the balance of energy received and consumed. If the body receives more energy than it expends, that is, if we receive more food than is necessary for normal human development, for work and well-being, we become fat. Now more than a third of our country, including children, is overweight. And there is only one reason - excess nutrition, which ultimately leads to atherosclerosis, coronary heart disease, hypertension, diabetes, and a number of other ailments.

Secondly, the diet should be varied and meet the needs for proteins, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals, and dietary fiber.

The following indicators of physical development are subject to assessment: somatometric (body length and weight, chest circumference), physiometric (muscle strength of the hands, vital capacity of the lungs) and somatoscopic indicators (assessment of the degree of puberty, number of permanent teeth).

The main methods for studying the physical development of a person are external examination (somatoscopy) and measurements - anthropometry (somatometry). The level of physical development and the degree of its harmony are determined using anthropometric research methods.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАННЫЕ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ:

1. Тураев, М. М. (2022). Оздоровительная физическая культура её основы и инновационные технологии. Science and Education, 3(4), 1102-1108.

2. Тураев, М. М. Образование и воспитание в сфере физической культуры-особенности повышения эффективности использования национальных ценностей. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. uz), 8(8).
3. Тураев, М. М. (2022, November). Организация проектных технологий на уроках физической культуры: 10.53885/edinres. 2022.61. 66.124 Тураев Махмуд Мухамедович Бухарский государственный университет, преподаватель. In Научно-практическая конференция (pp. 975-978).
4. Тураев, М. М. (2024). Сравнительная педагогика физической культуры, отрасль знания спорта и учебная дисциплина. *Science and Education*, 5(2), 335-340.
5. Тураев, М. М. (2024). Педагогическая технология в спортивной гимнастике, системы имитационного моделирования. *Science and Education*, 5(1), 332-337.
6. Тураев, М. М., Баймурадов, Р. С., & Файзиев, Я. З. (2020). Интерактивные методы физического воспитания в вузах. *Педагогическое образование и наука*, (3), 132-135.
7. Хамраев, И. Т., Курбанов, Д. И., & Тураев, М. М. (2021). Принципы современной педагогической подготовки. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(2), 899-907.
8. Тураев, М. М. (2021). Методы преподавания физического образования и их важные аспекты. *Проблемы науки*, (2 (61)), 35-37.
9. Тураев, М. М. (2021). Повышение эффективности физического воспитания студентов с помощью компьютерных технологий. *Вестник науки и образования*, (5-3 (118)), 99-102.
10. MM Turaev, VJ Boltayeva, SJ Razokova. **The importance of physical education and physical culture at schools**. *Вестник науки и образования* 1 (2-2 (122)), 34-37
11. Тураев, М. М. Теория и методика физической культуры. Учебное пособие, 1(1), 220.
12. Тураев, М. М. Методы преподавания социального образования и их важные аспекты. *Проблемы науки*, 35-37.
13. Маъмуров, Б. Б., & Тураев, М. М. (2023). Актуальные проблемы подготовки специалистов физического воспитания и спорта в современных условиях. In *Проблемы и перспективы развития спортивного образования, науки и практики* (pp. 134-142).
14. Тураев, М. М. (2022, November). Организация проектных технологий на уроках физической культуры: 10.53885/edinres. 2022.61. 66.124 Тураев Махмуд Мухамедович Бухарский государственный университет, преподаватель. In Научно-практическая конференция (pp. 975-978).
15. Баймурадов, Р. С., Файзиев, Я. З., & Тураев, М. М. (2019). Психологический анализ личности спортсмена. *Педагогическое образование и наука*, (6), 144-148.
16. Тураев, М. М. (2024). Сравнительная педагогика физической культуры, отрасль знания спорта и учебная дисциплина. *Science and Education*, 5(2), 335-340.
17. MM Тураев, ЭЮ Исломов. Организация и проведение оздоровительных занятий для людей пожилого возраста. *Физическая культура. Рекреация. Спорт*, 470-476
18. Тураев, М. М. (2024). Педагогическая технология в спортивной гимнастике, системы имитационного моделирования. *Science and Education*, 5(1), 332-337.
19. М Тураев. Important factors for the organization of medical groups in physical education. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz) 8 (8)

20. М Тураев. **Содержание процесса организации оздоровительных занятий для людей пожилого возраста.** Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz) 7 (7)
21. М Тураев. **Actual problems of teaching physical education at school.** Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. uz) 23 (23)
22. MM Turayev, BJQ Boltayeva. **Og'ma xulq-atvor o'rganish mahsuli sifatida.** Science and Education 3 (4), 1694-1701
23. MM Тураев. Теория и методика физической культуры. Вестник Бухарского государственного университета 1, 1 - 276
24. MM Тураев. Манипуляционное управление спортсменов - легкоатлетов спортивными модуляционно разработанными методами, приёмами. Science and Education 5 (3), 445-451
25. Alibek Botirovich Jo'Rayev (2024). Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida harakatli o'yinlar orqali jismoniy sifatlarni rivojlantirish (kurash)
26. Рахмон Равшанович Латипов. Проблемы и пути решения направления студентов к научной деятельности. Пиндский журнал культуры, литературы и ELT 3 (3), 42–47
27. Рахмон Равшанович Латипов (2024). Школьная аксиологическая подготовка учителя физической культуры на современном этапе эволюции. Science and Education, 5 (1), 299-304.
28. Рахмон Равшанович Латипов (2024). Философия спортивного искусства и образования в подготовке педагога-физической культуры. Science and Education, 5 (1), 292-298.
29. Latipov, R., & Ramazanov, M. (2023). Jismoniy madaniyat ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalarini kasbiy pedagogik madaniyatni tarbiyalashda tajriba-sinov ishlarining samaradorlik darajasi. *Молодые ученые*, 1(21), 37–40.
30. К.С. Колдошвич, Л.Р. Равшанович. Педагогические, психологические основы дентологической подготовки студентов высших учебных заведений (физическая культура). Американский журнал языка, грамотности и обучения в области STEM-образования 1 (2...